

THE DIFFERENCES OF AMERICAN AND GREAT BRITAIN ENGLISH
LANGUAGE PRONUNCIATION IN TRANSLATION

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Annotation: *This article represents the detailed information about English pronunciation in American and Great Britain. As an outcome it examines dissimilarities of pronunciations in the given countries.*

Key words: *pronunciation, dialects, type of pronunciation, spelling, American pronunciation, British pronunciation.*

Introduction. One of the essential features of the literary language, which distinguishes it from dialects, is the presence of more or less unified norms. The literary language has its own lexical, grammatical, spelling and pronunciation norms.

Pronunciation is the way in which a word or a language is spoken. A word can be spoken in different ways by various individuals or groups, depending on many factors, such as: the duration of the cultural exposure of their childhood, the location of their current residence, speech or voice disorders, their ethnic group, their social class, or their education.

In spoken English, we obviously use about a hundred sounds and variations in pitch, stress, pause, etc. Each sound is used with some modifications in real speech: for example, some people have full Irish, others have a very weak indication sound. The pronunciation of words varies considerably between regions where English is spoken, so that we can easily distinguish speakers by their pronunciation.

There are currently the following in Great Britain there are regional types of pronunciation: 1) Southern English pronunciation; 2) Northern English pronunciation; 3) Scottish pronunciation; 4) Irish pronunciation, among which Southern English pronunciation chosen as orthoepic modern English standard.[1]

There are at least three main speech directions in the USA: 1) Eastern type pronunciation; 2) Southern type; 3) Western general American type.

There are several obvious differences between American and British pronunciation.

1. The biggest difference between British English and American English is, undoubtedly, the accent. The most obvious difference between Standard American (GA) and Standard British (GB) is the omission of the "r" in GB: you only say <r> if it's followed by a vowel, so we don't say it. to PARK /pɑ:k/, HORSE /hɔ:s/ or FURTHER /'fɜ:ðə/. However, in American we pronounce every written /r/ as /pɑrk/, /hɔrs/ & /'fɜrðər/. [2]

2. Another difference is that British English retains the spelling of words borrowed from other languages, mainly French and German. Whereas the spelling of American English is mostly based on how the word sounds when it is spoken.

3. The melody of the British and Americans is very different, although the structure of speech is very similar. The most obvious difference is the British tendency to use a high falling intonation, striking the main accent up and down. Whereas in American, ascending tones are more common, so you go up from the main accent. This use of rising intonation in statements is sometimes referred to as "Upspeak".

4. /ɒ/ to /ɑ/ In British (GB) we use the back rounded open /ɒ/ for words like SHOP /ʃɒp/, LOST /lɒst/ and WANT /wɒnt/. In American (GA) we don't round the lips, so it's: /ʃɑp/, /last/ & /want/.

5. /ɑ/ to /ɛ/ The pronunciation and usage of /ɑ/ is quite similar between American and British; words like CAT and MAD are very similar. However, there is a group of words containing the spelling ARR, which changes from /ɑ/ to /ɛ/ in

American. CARRY /kari/ is /kəri/ EMBARRASS /ɪm'barɪs/ is /ɪm'berəs/ and HARRY /'hari/ is /'həri/ giving the name the same pronunciation as HAIRY in American. MARRY, MERRY and MARY would also be the same in American English, but different in British: /'mari/, /'məri/ & /'mɛ:ri/.

6. /ə:/ to /ɜr/ The sound of British thinking /ə:/ found in words like HEARD /hɜ:d/, FIRST /fɜ:st/ and WORST /wɜ:st/ is pronounced differently - with raised tongue and /r/ quality in American, /hɜrd/, /fɜrst / & /wɜrst/. The spelling of this sound almost always includes the letter "r", but even when it is not, Americans pronounce the unit, as in the word COLONEL /'kɜnəl/, which in British English sounds like /'kə:nəl/.

7. /ɔ:/ to /ɔr/ & /ɑ/ Long back rounded /ɔ:/ as in SWORD /sɔ:d/, POWER /fɔ:s/, THOUGHT /θɔ:t/ and LAW /lɔ:/ in American are pronounced in two ways. /ɔr/ for words with "r", so SWORD /sɔrd/ and POWER /fɔrs/, and /ɑ/ for words without /r/, so THOUGHT /θɑt/ and LAW /lɑ/. This means that for many American speakers COT /kat/ and CAUGHT /kat/ are the same, although COURT /kɔrt/ would be different. In British English CAUGHT /kɔ:t/ and COURT are the same, COT /kɒt/ are different.

8. /t/ When /t/ appears after a stressed vowel and before a weak vowel, American speakers often make a voiced wave - a bit like a very fast /d/: WATER, FIGHT, GET IT. In standard British, this would be pronounced as normal /t/ WATER, FIGHT, GET, although in regional British accents, especially Cockney, it would be a glottal stop: WATER, FIGHT, GOT.[3]

To sum up, I have found out that although both American and Great Britain English language pronunciation differentiate from each other notably , they both play crucial role not only in spoken language but also in translation.

The list of used literature:

1. Abduazizov A.A. English Phonetics , Tashkent , 2007 , p. 61-62
2. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://pronunciationstudio.com/american-vs-british-pronunciation/&ved=2ahUKEwjxi4Lnh8b7AhVJ9DgGHfbWdN8QFnoECDCQAQ&usg=AOvVaw3Fench0356-156eMS9hwXUx>
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